

Supplemental Table S1 Differentially expressed proteins (variations >2.0 fold, P < 0.05) in TOF and non-TOF right

No.	IPI accession number(a)	Gene symbol	Protein	Seq. cov (%) (c)	TOF spectrum count	Non-TOF spectrum count(b)	Fold change	P-value
1	IPI00022895	A1BG	Alpha-1B-glycoprotein	46.78	33.06 ± 15.75	13.12 ± 5.12	2.52	0.0158
2	IPI00479760	AAK1	AP2-associated protein kinase 1	29.82	69.98 ± 35.76	32.68 ± 3.336	2.14	0.0034
3	IPI00009532	ABAT	4-Aminobutyrate aminotransferase, mitochondrial	39.17	27.93 ± 2.19	164.46 ± 11.98	0.17	0.0256
4	IPI00479296	ABCA8	ATP-binding cassette sub-family A member	66.07	15.51 ± 4.92	52.75 ± 3.88	0.29	0.0352
5	IPI00894097	AEBP1	Adipocyte enhancer-binding protein 1	12.30	4.68 ± 1.07	24.64 ± 2.19	0.19	0.0436
6	IPI00016568	AK4	Adenylate kinase isoenzyme 4,	19.78	71.39 ± 14.38	145.84 ± 7.47	0.49	0.002
7	IPI00940222	AKAP12	A-kinase anchor protein 12	54.93	34.13 ± 3.16	74.47 ± 3.64	0.46	0.0066
8	IPI00965719	ANK2	Ankyrin-2	64.85	12.41 ± 2.46	49.65 ± 5.31	0.25	0.0016
9	IPI00514053	ARCN1	Coatomer subunit delta	20.75	3.10 ± 1.04	31.03 ± 3.87	0.1	0.04
10	IPI00418431	ASPN	Asporin	48.81	124.12 ± 10.97	319.61 ± 11.71	0.39	0.0107
11	IPI00010790	BGN	Biglycan	69.04	102.40 ± 4.39	335.12 ± 18.92	0.3	0.0453
12	IPI00021727	C4BPA	C4b-binding protein alpha	25.39	38.55 ± 4.64	16.26 ± 2.194	2.37	0.0001
13	IPI00022395	C9	Complement component C9	23.86	145.75 ± 32.21	131.82 ± 5.93	4.58	0.0257
14	IPI00843811	C9orf123	Transmembrane protein C9orf123	18.94	46.54 ± 17.32	6.21 ± 1.96	7.5	0.0070
15	IPI00027466	CA4	Carbonic anhydrase 4	26.06	6.21 ± 2.17	43.44 ± 3.93	0.14	0.0150
16	IPI00465436	CAT	Catalase	74.63	192.38 ± 15.36	58.96 ± 7.08	3.26	0.0104
17	IPI00027626	CCT6A	T-complex protein 1 subunit zeta	63.95	80.68 ± 32.18	167.56 ± 8.55	0.48	0.0176
18	IPI00010180	CES1	Liver carboxylesterase 1	23.00	12.41 ± 3.54	52.75 ± 5.28	0.24	0.0324
19	IPI00009028	CLEC3B	Tetranectin	64.24	3.10 ± 1.21	37.24 ± 3.52	0.08	0.0162
20	IPI00024776	CLGN	Calmegin	29.54	31.03 ± 12.86	65.16 ± 3.09	0.48	0.0287
21	IPI00400826	CLU	Clusterin	39.63	12.41 ± 4.32	71.37 ± 5.86	0.17	0.0045
22	IPI00176193	COL14A1	Collagen alpha-1(XIV) chain	62.16	217.21 ± 34.21	1471.65 ± 18.55	0.46	0.0131
23	IPI00856012	COL6A6	Collagen alpha-6(VI) chain	54.33	83.78 ± 32.12	226.52 ± 12.16	0.37	0.0085
24	IPI00163230	COPS6	COP9 signalosome	33.51	15.51 ± 32.34	71.37 ± 3.88	0.22	0.0049
25	IPI00645720	COQ7	Ubiquinone biosynthesis	23.23	34.13 ± 12.09	102.40 ± 8.78	0.33	0.0023
26	IPI00017601	CP	Ceruloplasmin	35.86	117.91 ± 38.79	245.14 ± 15.51	0.48	0.0072
27	IPI00917030	CPVL	Probable serine protease inhibitor	12.36	3.10 ± 0.83	43.44 ± 5.70	0.07	0.0490
28	IPI00031801	CSDA	DNA-binding protein A	28.16	31.03 ± 14.28	3.10 ± 0.98	10.01	0.0036
29	IPI00002824	CSRP2	Cysteine and glycine-rich protein 2	62.92	39.07 ± 8.67	11.25 ± 2.29	3.47	0.0004

30	IPI00012835	CTBP1	C-terminal-binding protein 1	12.98	18.62 ± 5.43	89.99 ± 6.45	0.21	0.0082
31	IPI00010120	CTBP2	C-terminal-binding protein 2	50.33	6.21 ± 2.14	24.82 ± 2.45	0.25	0.0023
32	IPI00019411	CYP2J2	Cytochrome P450 2 J2	50.64	34.13 ± 23.56	3.10 ± 0.96	11	0.0441
33	IPI00028387	DDRGK1	DDRGK domain-containing protein	18.73	3.10 ± 1.24	34.13 ± 3.09	0.09	0.0085
34	IPI00024462	DHODH	Dihydroorotate dehydrogenase	36.44	46.36 ± 2.45	18.67 ± 5.32	2.48	0.0203
35	IPI00454647	DHRS4-A	Putative uncharacterized Putative pre-mRNA-splicing factor	14.33	18.14 ± 7.63	7.85 ± 2.27	2.31	0.0005
36	IPI00396435	DHX15	ATP-dependent RNA helicase DHX15	68.99	18.62 ± 9.21	55.85 ± 4.58	0.33	0.0015
37	IPI00465105	DNAJA4	DnaJ homolog subfamily A member 4	34.78	34.13 ± 12.34	3.10 ± 0.92	11.00	0.0109
38	IPI00556073	DNAJB6	DnaJ homolog subfamily B member 6	15.84	71.37 ± 22.98	21.72 ± 2.94	3.28	0.0162
39	IPI00220813	EFEMP1	EGF-containing fibulin-like	68.99	9.31 ± 3.01	43.44 ± 3.64	0.21	0.0480
40	IPI00003519	EFTUD2	116 kDa U5 small nuclear	48.92	18.62 ± 2.90	49.65 ± 2.98	0.38	0.0009
41	IPI00102069	EIF3M	Eukaryotic translation	59.52	37.24 ± 14.32	3.10 ± 1.02	12.00	0.0385
42	IPI00411704	EIF5A	Eukaryotic translation initiation factor 5A-1	52.33	21.72 ± 6.82	93.09 ± 6.03	0.23	0.0079
43	IPI00012510	EMILIN2	EMILIN-2	49.24	102.40 ± 41.05	49.65 ± 3.64	2.06	0.0352
44	IPI00303161	ESAM	Endothelial cell-selective adhesion molecule	13.31	46.54 ± 32.12	6.21 ± 1.96	7.50	0.0183
45	IPI00297550	F13A1	Coagulation factor XIII A chain	25.44	21.72 ± 12.23	58.96 ± 2.71	0.37	0.0316
46	IPI00019568	F2	Prothrombin	46.86	37.24 ± 7.18	105.50 ± 6.735	0.35	0.0345
47	IPI00294615	FBLN5	Fibulin-5	61.22	52.75 ± 20.94	136.53 ± 5.70	0.39	0.0038
48	IPI00298497	FGB	Fibrinogen beta chain	28.04	77.57 ± 25.10	207.90 ± 16.90	0.37	0.0186
49	IPI00021891	FGG	Fibrinogen gamma chain	30.30	127.22 ± 40.18	269.96 ± 12.42	0.47	0.0083
50	IPI00293425	FXN	Frataxin, mitochondrial	66.55	12.41 ± 3.85	49.65 ± 3.65	0.25	0.0053
51	IPI00968027	GC	Vitamin D-binding protein	74.40	37.24 ± 18.3	86.88 ± 15.43	0.43	0.0327
52	IPI00333763	GLRX5	Glutaredoxin-related protein 5,	68.63	24.82 ± 15.43	55.85 ± 3.81	0.44	0.0032
53	IPI00215687	GLS	Glutaminase kidney isoform, High density	35.01	52.75 ± 13.45	21.72 ± 2.55	2.43	0.0225
54	IPI00894287	HDLBP	lipoprotein binding protein	50.33	61.66 ± 13.54	13.85 ± 3.46	4.45	0.0004

55	IPI00003566	HOMER1	Homer protein homolog 1	34.71	3.10 ± 0.24	31.03 ± 3.27	0.1	0.0001
56	IPI00477597	HPR	Haptoglobin-related protein	33.77	6.21 ± 2.40	49.65 ± 5.70	0.13	0.0431
57	IPI00022488	HPX	Hemopexin	23.40	167.56 ± 15.27	341.33 ± 14.62	0.49	0.0057
58	IPI00555565	HSP90AB2	heat shock protein HSP 90-beta 4	27.21	101.54 ± 36.42	32.75 ± 27.54	3.1	0.0100
59	IPI00217474	IFI16	Gamma-interferon-	14.87	37.24 ± 9.40	9.31 ± 4.06	4	0.0152
60	IPI00018300	IFIT1	Interferon-induced protein with	44.35	22.99 ± 4.98	8.32 ± 3.68	2.76	0.0100
61	IPI00423461	IGHA2	Ig alpha-2 chain C region	36.08	41.65 ± 15.43	14.29 ± 2.19	2.91	0.0078
62	IPI00896380	IGHM	Ig mu chain C region	49.94	3.10 ± 0.68	62.06 ± 6.72	0.05	0.0124
63	IPI00005198	ILF2	Interleukin enhancer-binding factor 2	52.32	43.44 ± 11.48	117.91 ± 6.51	0.37	0.0385
64	IPI00032328	KNG1	Kininogen-1	21.13	9.31 ± 2.17	52.75 ± 24.63	0.18	0.048
65	IPI00299033	KPNA3	Importin subunit alpha-3	71.77	18.62 ± 3.50	46.54 ± 2.19	0.4	0.0027
66	IPI00012578	KPNA4	Importin subunit alpha-4	72.57	12.41 ± 4.38	43.44 ± 13.93	0.29	0.0287
67	IPI00386803	LASP1	LIM and SH3 domain protein 1	50.55	18.62 ± 4.54	49.65 ± 12.00	0.38	0.0164
68	IPI00419643	LCLAT1	Lysocardiolipin acyltransferase 1	36.82	11.92 ± 2.36	42.05 ± 2.17	0.28	0.01
69	IPI00009950	LMAN2	Vesicular integral-membrane protein VIP36	35.24	3.10 ± 0.73	24.82 ± 2.85	0.13	0.0361
70	IPI00027847	LPL	Lipoprotein Leucine-rich	25.08	6.21 ± 3.67	24.82 ± 12.45	0.25	0.0499
71	IPI00386687	LRRFIP1	repeat flightlessinteractin g protein 1	29.71	31.03 ± 2.65	6.21 ± 1.31	5.00	0.0392
72	IPI00020986	LUM	Lumican	27.78	39.09 ± 12.87	81.29 ± 30.11	0.48	0.0038
73	IPI00107722	MCEE	Methylmalonyl-CoA epimerase, mitochondrial	23.11	56.42 ± 16.54	16.34 ± 2.16	3.45	0.0021
74	IPI00022300	METTL7A	Methyltransferase-like protein 7A	73.86	12.41 ± 2.28	52.75 ± 4.64	0.24	0.0116
75	IPI00654820	MT-ATP6	ATP synthase subunit a	73.25	3.10 ± 0.35	27.93 ± 2.29	0.11	0.0085
76	IPI00102685	MYADM	Myeloid-associated differentiation	50.27	40.33 ± 7.15	9.31 ± 2.09	4.33	0.0332
77	IPI00790503	MYH10	Myosin-10	58.80	108.60 ± 24.65	217.21 ± 31.92	0.5	0.0407
78	IPI00760846	MYO18A	Myosin-XVIIIa Nascent	33.78	52.75 ± 32.65	114.81 ± 7.32	0.46	0.0261
79	IPI00797126	NACA	polypeptide-associated complex	17.89	148.94 ± 54.71	174.47 ± 5.12	2	0.0401
80	IPI00926519	NAGK	N-acetyl-D-glucosamine	41.66	6.21 ± 2.36	24.82 ± 2.19	0.25	0.0401
81	IPI00293817	NAPG	Gamma-soluble NSF attachment protein	44.56	13.67 ± 8.16	3.56 ± 3.09	3.84	0.0145

82	IPI00855737	NEXN	Nexilin	17.66	9.31 ± 3.17	34.13 ± 6.23	0.27	0.0314
83	IPI00465264	NLRX1	NLR family member X1	45.79	40.34 ± 13.82	93.09 ± 6.21	0.43	0.0352
84	IPI00299000	PA2G4	Proliferation-associated protein 2G4	75.50	43.44 ± 20.62	9.31 ± 1.50	4.67	0.0229
85	IPI00221111	PACSIN2	Protein kinase C and casein kinase	37.28	6.21 ± 1.60	49.65 ± 23.93	0.13	0.0227
86	IPI00980056	PACSIN3	Protein kinase C and casein kinase	33.48	15.51 ± 4.29	68.27 ± 15.62	0.23	0.0480
87	IPI00298547	PARK7	Protein DJ-1	63.55	77.57 ± 18.24	24.82 ± 4.09	3.125	0.0120
88	IPI00167134	PDLIM3	PDZ and LIM domain protein 3	60.28	12.41 ± 3.16	89.99 ± 17.52	0.14	0.0134
89	IPI00220808	PFKFB2	6-Phosphofructo-2-kinase/fructose-2,6-bisphosphatase 2	32.04	34.13 ± 7.82	6.21 ± 1.31	5.5	0.0351
90	IPI00299977	PHPT1	14 kDa phosphohistidine phosphatase	52.58	15.51 ± 5.92	43.44 ± 2.62	0.36	0.0273
91	IPI00216694	PLS3	Plastin-3	46.59	58.96 ± 18.65	145.84 ± 11.71	0.4	0.0055
92	IPI00744711	PNPT1	Polyribonucleotide nucleotidyltransferase 1,	30.99	43.44 ± 32.59	102.40 ± 6.04	0.42	0.0227
93	IPI00165506	POLDIP2	Polymerase delta-interacting protein	19.09	108.81 ± 45.36	28.17 ± 2.45	3.86	0.0354
94	IPI00470502	PPA2	Inorganic pyrophosphatase 2,	32.01	74.47 ± 23.43	152.05 ± 6.93	0.49	0.0088
95	IPI00439948	PPP1R13L	mitochondrial RelA-associated inhibitor	41.25	40.33 ± 12.75	9.31 ± 1.53	4.33	0.048
96	IPI00295252	PREX1	Phosphatidylinositol 3,4,5-trisphosphate-dependent Rac	54.17	31.03 ± 14.58	6.21 ± 1.31	5.00	0.0388
97	IPI00305068	PRPF6	Pre-mRNA-processing factor	28.27	48.86 ± 17.47	17.94 ± 2.19	2.72	0.0092
98	IPI00024821	PSMD14	26S proteasome non-ATPase regulatory subunit 14	53.03	27.92 ± 8.22	65.16 ± 4.25	0.43	0.0186
99	IPI00856076	PUF60	Poly(U)-binding-splicing factor PUF60	24.81	40.33 ± 9.78	12.41 ± 3.00	3.25	0.024
100	IPI00016339	RAB5C	Ras-related protein Rab-5C	54.09	40.33 ± 13.64	80.68 ± 4.19	0.5	0.0054
101	IPI00024320	RBM3	Putative RNA-binding protein 3	61.81	28.50 ± 2.78	12.48 ± 4.57	2.28	0.0108
102	IPI00219335	RPL3L	60S ribosomal protein L3-like	61.89	40.34 ± 17.49	12.41 ± 2.17	3.25	0.0073
103	IPI00003918	RPL4	60S ribosomal protein L4	51.06	80.68 ± 29.90	15.51 ± 2.64	5.2	0.0046
104	IPI00221088	RPS9	40S ribosomal protein S9	31.78	89.55 ± 33.43	16.83 ± 2.62	5.32	0.0036

105	IPI00012512	RRAS2	Ras-related protein R-Ras2	56.66	24.82 ± 4.69	3.10 ± 0.97	8	0.0072
106	IPI00220558	RYR1	Ryanodine receptor 1	67.02	18.62 ± 4.50	55.85 ± 5.02	0.33	0.0206
107	IPI00329784	RYR3	Ryanodine receptor 3	52.02	46.54 ± 16.07	18.62 ± 2.61	2.5	0.0403
108	IPI00022275	SACM1L	Phosphatidylinositide phosphatase SAC1	74.87	9.31 ± 1.72	37.24 ± 2.85	0.25	0.0197
109	IPI00062266	SCRN2	Secernin-2	74.50	43.44 ± 32.12	9.31 ± 1.50	4.67	0.0375
110	IPI00847635	SERPINA3	Alpha-1-antichymotrypsin	22.67	9.31 ± 1.01	62.06 ± 5.27	0.15	0.0006
111	IPI00027482	SERPINA6	Corticosteroid-binding globulin	13.48	6.21 ± 12.32	24.82 ± 2.45	0.25	0.0041
112	IPI00293074	SLC44A2	Choline transporter-like	22.29	15.51 ± 4.34	52.75 ± 2.94	0.29	0.0269
113	IPI00893850	SMTN	Smoothelin	71.10	31.03 ± 3.83	9.31 ± 1.48	3.33	0.0215
114	IPI00299095	SNX2	Sorting nexin-2	73.03	9.31 ± 6.94	34.13 ± 2.75	0.27	0.0453
115	IPI00291419	SOAT2	Sterol O-acyltransferase 2	25.50	3.10 ± 0.35	27.93 ± 3.05	0.11	0.0261
116	IPI00027827	SOD3	Extracellular superoxide dismutase [Cu-Zn]	35.07	55.85 ± 13.88	111.71 ± 35.51	0.5	0.0287
117	IPI00103415	STAT5B	Signal transducer and activator of transcription 5B	47.16	3.10 ± 0.85	27.93 ± 3.06	0.11	0.0352
118	IPI00019903	TACO1	Translational activator of cytochrome c oxidase 1	29.40	37.24 ± 11.85	96.19 ± 5.52	0.39	0.0344
119	IPI00386607	TBCD	Tubulin-specific chaperone D	41.48	83.05 ± 34.85	35.12 ± 3.09	2.36	0.0130
120	IPI00160479	TECRL	Trans-2,3-enoyl-CoA reductase-Tensin-like C1	56.55	6.21 ± 2.84	37.24 ± 8.07	0.17	0.0458
121	IPI00385317	TENC1	domain-containing phosphatase	44.02	28.80 ± 10.35	10.96 ± 2.64	2.63	0.0209
122	IPI00022462	TFRC	Transferrin receptor protein 1	57.83	161.36 ± 57.91	68.27 ± 4.09	2.36	0.0261
123	IPI00794391	THSD4	Thrombospondin type-1 domain-containing protein 4	45.66	6.21 ± 2.32	37.24 ± 3.81	0.17	0.0147
124	IPI00001541	TIMM9	Mitochondrial import inner membrane translocase subunit Tim9	12.09	3.10 ± 0.53	21.72 ± 2.56	0.14	0.0199
125	IPI00063130	TMEM205	Transmembrane protein 205	37.26	21.72 ± 9.38	46.54 ± 2.19	0.47	0.0499

126	IPI00005087	TMOD3	Tropomodulin-3 Thioredoxin- related	43.50	149.04 ± 48.23	73.02 ± 2.29	2.04	0.0383
127	IPI00100247	TMX4	transmembrane protein 4	37.78	159.74 ± 33.85	37.90 ± 3.57	4.21	0.0052
128	IPI00939667	TPP1	Tripeptidyl- peptidase 1	34.68	74.47 ± 3.56	148.94 ± 35.63	0.50	0.0344
129	IPI00301561	TRIP6	Thyroid receptor- interacting protein	44.04	27.93 ± 3.43	3.10 ± 0.89	9.00	0.0199
130	IPI00292858	TYMP	Thymidine phosphorylase	40	21.11 ± 11.26	7.29 ± 4.57	2.89	0.0397
131	IPI00830039	U2AF2	Splicing factor U2AF 65 kDa subunit	18	15.51 ± 9.34	40.34 ± 2.65	0.38	0.0480
132	IPI00003965	USP7	Ubiquitin carboxyl-terminal	30	27.96 ± 16.28	9.16 ± 2.19	3.05	0.0200
133	IPI00215631	VCAN	Versican core protein	72	71.37 ± 36.73	170.66 ± 8.56	0.42	0.0034
134	IPI00032050	WBP2	WW domain- binding protein 2	14	34.13 ± 8.73	3.10 ± 0.99	10.00	0.0131
135	IPI00922067	XPNPEP3	Probable Xaa-Pro aminopeptidase 3 Zinc-binding alcohol	15	3.10 ± 1.58	31.03 ± 2.94	0.10	0.0230
136	IPI00166738	ZADH2	dehydrogenase domain-containing protein 2	30	34.13 ± 5.07	3.10 ± 0.87	11.00	0.0333

a:Accession number from EMBL-EBI (International Protein Index, IPI); b:Scores based on the average of each sample's spectral counting; c:Percentage of sequence coverage